

A nearly-conservative, high-order, forward Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of compressible flows on unstructured triangular meshes

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Abstract

In this work, we present a novel Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of compressible and inviscid flows. The scheme considers: (i) high-order continuous space discretizations on unstructured triangular meshes, (ii) high-order implicit–explicit Runge–Kutta schemes for the time discretization, (iii) conservation of mass, momentum and total energy, as long as some integrals in the formulation are computed exactly, and (iv) subgrid-stabilization and discontinuity-capturing operators based on Brenner’s model [*Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 370 (2006), pp. 190-224] for viscous flows. The method has been tested on several benchmark problems using a fourth-order time-marching formula and up to fifth-order continuous finite elements, yielding the expected results both for smooth and discontinuous solutions.

Keywords: finite element method, Lagrangian–Eulerian method, compressible flows, high-order methods, triangular meshes, discontinuity-capturing

1. Introduction

The development of finite element methods for the computation of compressible flows is an extensive topic of research nowadays due to their many applications in industry and science, e.g., aircraft design [1], turbomachinery [2] and heat transfer [3].

Among the finite element methods found in the literature, we can first distinguish the so-called pure Lagrangian methods, in which the computational mesh is moved forward-in-time with the local fluid velocity. As advantages with respect to fixed-mesh (Eulerian) methods, the convective terms of the equations are naturally stabilized, the CFL condition is less restrictive and the shocks and free surfaces are easily tracked. However, these methods suffer from mesh distortion problems under the presence of large gradients in the velocity field. Arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) methods [4] alleviate this drawback either by smoothing the mesh and remapping the solution –Lagrangian+remap type– or by directly moving the mesh with a smoother velocity field –monolithic or direct type. As examples of Lagrangian and ALE methods for compressible flows, we mention the staggered grid method of Dobrev et al. [5, 6], the nodal methods of Scovazzi and co-workers [7–12], Guermond et al. [13–15] and Cremonesi and Frangi [16], the ADER-DG method of Boscheri and Dumbser [17], and the staggered grid residual distribution method of Abgrall et al. [18, 19].

Other families of methods which are somehow similar in nature to ALE schemes, but are often considered separately, are the so-called semi-Lagrangian [20] and Lagrange–Galerkin methods [21–23]. In these

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algorithms, the material derivatives are discretized (typically) backward-in-time along the fluid trajectories. Then, the information of some of the previously computed solutions is transferred from a background reference mesh to a backward-in-time displaced mesh either by interpolation –semi-Lagrangian methods– or by more accurate L^2 projections [24] –Lagrange–Galerkin methods. Hence, mesh distortion problems are avoided and, as with pure Lagrangian methods, the convective terms in the equations are naturally stabilized.

Most part of the Lagrange–Galerkin methods available in the literature lack conservation properties and are second-order accurate in time. However, they can be made conservative through the so-called *weak Lagrange–Galerkin* formulation [21], which is of great help to adequately capture and track discontinuities in the solution. This formulation was first introduced by Benqué et al. [25, 26] and employed later by Giraldo [27, 28], Kaazempur-Mofrad et al. [29, 30] and Colera et al. [31, 32], and achieves conservation by enforcing that the weighting functions be constant along the trajectories of the fluid particles. Thus, it is somehow similar to that of some versions of the Eulerian–Lagrangian localized adjoint method (ELLAM) [33, 34] and to that employed in some Lagrangian methods such as [6]. Furthermore, some authors have proposed to integrate the fluid trajectories forward-in-time [32, 35–38] –as usual in ALE methods– to allow for an efficient and simple implementation of higher-order time-marching schemes.

Though Lagrange–Galerkin methods have been successfully employed for the resolution of many interesting problems such as the incompressible Navier–Stokes equations [22, 39–41], the shallow water equations [27, 28, 42] and combustion [43, 44], we are not aware of their application to compressible flows.

It is interesting to note that forward Lagrange–Galerkin schemes and ALE methods of Lagrangian+remap type are very similar. The main difference is that, in the former schemes, the solution is remapped onto a fixed reference mesh via L^2 projections, instead of onto a smoothed Lagrangian mesh via some remapping techniques [45, 46]. Therefore, as also remarked by [38], it seems that pure Lagrangian and semi-Lagrangian methods, which were quite different in nature at their origins, are evolving towards the same point. Due to this similitude, and also for simplicity, hereafter we shall consider forward Lagrange–Galerkin methods as another class of ALE methods.

In this work, we propose a novel forward Lagrange–Galerkin scheme for the resolution of two-dimensional, compressible and inviscid flows, which is an extension of our previous work [32] for scalar hyperbolic conservation laws. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first Lagrangian-type method in the literature which considers, at the same time, (i) high-order, continuous space discretizations on unstructured triangular meshes, (ii) high-order time discretizations, and (iii) conservation of mass, momentum and total energy irrespective of the employed time-marching scheme, as long as some integrals in the formulation are computed exactly.

The motivation for unstructured triangular meshes comes from the fact that, as pointed by [11, 16, 42], these are more amenable for automatic mesh generation and remeshing than quadrilateral ones, and also allow for an easier coupling with state-of-the-art codes for electromagnetism and other physics. On the other hand, high-order elements are able to capture shocks within a smaller number of elements [47] and have better scaling properties in parallel computations [48]. Furthermore, continuous space discretizations lead to a smaller number of degrees of freedom and thus require less memory than the widely employed discontinuous Galerkin approximations [49, 50]. Finally, it is clear that preservation of mass, momentum and total energy and the possibility to employ high-order time discretizations are also desirable properties.

Another interesting feature of the proposed method is the usage of Brenner’s model [51] to regularize the Euler equations instead of the more common Navier–Stokes model, following, e.g. [13, 52, 53]. In contrast to the latter, Brenner’s regularization satisfies entropy principles and positivity of the density and the internal energy [54], and provides better numerical results [52]. Starting from this model, we extend the subgrid stabilization techniques in [55, 56] to remove acoustic instabilities and develop a residual-based operator to detect and capture the discontinuities in the solution.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the weak formulation for the continuous problem and explains its numerical discretization. In Section 3, some numerical experiments are performed to address the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method. Finally, Section 4 discusses some conclusions and possible future works.

2. Formulation and discretization

In this work, we focus on the Euler equations for compressible and inviscid flows,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho v_j)}{\partial x_j} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial m_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (m_i v_j)}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{E}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\mathcal{E} v_j)}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial (p v_j)}{\partial x_j}, \quad (3)$$

with $t \in [0, T]$ the time, $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2] \in \Omega$ the position vector, ρ the density, $\mathbf{v} = [v_1, v_2]$ the velocity, $\mathbf{m} = \rho \mathbf{v}$ the momentum per unit of volume, p the pressure, $\mathcal{E} = p/(\gamma - 1) + \rho v_i v_i/2$ the total energy per unit of volume and γ the adiabatic constant of the gas. The fluid variables are functions of (\mathbf{x}, t) and Einstein's summation convention for tensor operations is adopted. The system (1)-(3) is subject to the initial conditions

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \rho^0(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \mathbf{m}^0(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \mathcal{E}^0(\mathbf{x}),$$

and to appropriate boundary conditions.

The conservative, weak Lagrange-Galerkin formulation of Eqs. (1)-(3) is [28, 31]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega_f} \rho \psi \, d\Omega = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega_f} m_i \psi \, d\Omega = \int_{\Omega_f} p \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_i} \, d\Omega - \oint_{\partial \Omega_f} p \psi n_i \, d\sigma, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega_f} \mathcal{E} \psi \, d\Omega = \int_{\Omega_f} p v_j \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x_j} \, d\Omega - \oint_{\partial \Omega_f} p v_j \psi n_j \, d\sigma, \quad (6)$$

where $\Omega_f = \Omega_f(t) \subseteq \Omega$ is an arbitrary domain that moves with the velocity field –i.e., a *fluid domain*–, n_i is the outward normal vector to $\partial \Omega_f$ and $\psi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a continuous test function such that $D\psi/Dt := \partial \psi / \partial t + v_i \partial \psi / \partial x_i = 0$. Note that Eqs. (4)-(6) can be interpreted from a physical point of view as conservation equations for a *weighted mass*, a *weighted momentum* and a *weighted energy*, and that the classical conservation laws of mass, momentum and energy are a particular case in which $\psi \equiv 1$.

In what follows, $(\cdot)^n$ refers to any variable evaluated at a given time t^n , $\partial_t \equiv \partial / \partial t$, $\partial_i \equiv \partial / \partial x_i$ and

$$(u, v)_D = \int_D uv \, d\Omega, \quad \langle u, v \rangle_{\partial D} = \oint_{\partial D} uv \, d\sigma,$$

denote respectively the scalar product of two generic functions u and v over a generic domain D and over its boundary ∂D .

2.1. Space discretization

The space discretization employed here is very similar to that of our previous work [31]. Thus, for completeness, we provide here a brief description of it and refer the reader to this reference for further details.

Let Ω_h be a polygonal domain that approximates the fixed domain Ω . We consider an admissible decomposition \mathbb{T}_h of Ω_h into isoparametric triangles, with the nodes distributed according to a Chebyshev grid of the second kind [57] to allow for stable high-order discretizations. The finite element space V_h associated with \mathbb{T}_h is the direct sum of a *large-scale space*, \bar{V}_h , and a *fine-scale space*, V'_h , –i.e., $V_h = \bar{V}_h \oplus V'_h$ –, so that any function $\psi_h \in V_h$ is expressed as the sum

$$\psi_h = \bar{\psi}_h + \psi'_h, \quad (7)$$

113 of a *large-scale term*, $\bar{\psi}_h \in \bar{V}_h$, and a *fine-scale term*, $\psi'_h \in V'_h$. This is done with a view to employ subgrid
114 stabilization techniques [55, 56, 58] as well as the discontinuity-capturing operator developed later.

115 The large-scale space is the well-known space spanned by the continuous Lagrange polynomials –of degree
116 r – associated with the mesh nodes, i.e., $\bar{V}_h = P_r(\mathbb{T}_h)$, with r the order of the space discretization. The
117 fine-scale space is the part of the space spanned by the products of the standard bubble function with
118 the basis functions of $P_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ that is not already contained in $P_r(\mathbb{T}_h)$, i.e., $V'_h = B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ –see also
119 [58]. More specifically, let $\widehat{K} := \{\widehat{\mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^2 : 0 \leq \widehat{x}_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq \widehat{x}_2 \leq 1 - \widehat{x}_1\}$ be the well-known reference triangle, $\widehat{b} =$
120 $27(1 - \widehat{x}_1 - \widehat{x}_2)\widehat{x}_1\widehat{x}_2$ the bubble function, $\widehat{\mathbf{x}}$ the coordinate vector in \widehat{K} and $\widehat{P}_r(\widehat{K})$ the space of polynomials
121 in \widehat{K} of maximal degree r . The standard isoparametric transformation from \widehat{K} to a given element $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$ is

$$\mathbf{F}_K : \widehat{\mathbf{x}} \in \widehat{K} \longrightarrow \mathbf{x} \in K, \quad \mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} \mathbf{x}_{n_k} \widehat{L}_k(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}),$$

122 where N_v is the number of nodes of the element, n_k is the k th local node of K and $\widehat{L}_k(\widehat{\mathbf{x}})$ is the Lagrange
123 polynomial associated with n_k . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_h = P_r(\mathbb{T}_h) &:= \{\psi \in C^0(\Omega_h) : \psi|_K = \widehat{p} \circ \mathbf{F}_K^{-1}, \widehat{p} \in \widehat{P}_r(\widehat{K}), \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h\}, \\ V'_h = B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h) &:= \{\psi \in C^0(\Omega_h) : \psi|_K = (\widehat{b}\widehat{p}) \circ \mathbf{F}_K^{-1}, \widehat{p} \in \widehat{P}_{r-1}(\widehat{K}), \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h\} - P_r(\mathbb{T}_h), \end{aligned}$$

124 and $V_h = P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\mathbb{T}_h) := P_r(\mathbb{T}_h) \oplus B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$. Recall that the functions in $B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ cancel at the edges of
125 the elements.

126 As it will be shown later, the reference mesh Ω_h is to be displaced in a Lagrangian fashion from a
127 reference time t^n to a generic time $t \geq t^n$. For that purpose, it is convenient to introduce some notation
128 and to recall some important properties of the conservative Lagrange–Galerkin method. Let $\chi_N(t)$ be the
129 trajectory of the N th mesh node \mathbf{x}_N , which evolves according to the system

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\chi_N(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{v}(\chi_N(t), t), & t \geq t^n, \\ \chi_N(t^n) = \mathbf{x}_N. \end{cases}$$

130 Assuming for the moment that the trajectories of the mesh nodes are known, then [32] (see also Fig. 1):

131 (i) For each element $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$, an isoparametric, curvilinear, *convected element* $\widetilde{K}_h(t)$ is defined from the
132 convected nodes of K . That is, $\widetilde{K}_h(t)$ is the image of the isoparametric transformation

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{F}}_K : \widehat{\mathbf{x}} \in \widehat{K}, t \in [t^n, \infty) \longrightarrow \mathbf{x} \in \widetilde{K}_h(t), \quad \mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_v} \chi_{n_k}(t) \widehat{L}_k(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}).$$

133 At the same time, the union of convected elements defines a *convected mesh* $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$ and a *convected*
134 *domain* $\widetilde{\Omega}_h(t)$. We assume that the time step $t - t^n$ is small enough to avoid distortion of the elements
135 in $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$.

136 (ii) The *convected finite element space* $\widetilde{V}_h(t) = P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t))$ is defined. Note that the latter is a standard
137 polynomial–bubble space, although it is defined in the curvilinear, convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$. Also note
138 that $\widetilde{V}_h^n \equiv V_h$.

139 (iii) The position of a fluid particle initially –i.e., at t^n – at \mathbf{x} is approximated by $\mathbf{X}_h(\mathbf{x}, t) = \widetilde{\mathbf{F}}_K(\mathbf{F}_K^{-1}(\mathbf{x}), t)$.

140 (iv) If $\psi_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a function such that $D\psi_h/Dt = 0$, then it is assumed that $\psi_h(\mathbf{X}_h(\mathbf{x}, t), t) = \psi_h^n(\mathbf{x})$ or,
141 mapping back to the reference element,

$$\psi_h|_{\widetilde{K}_h(t)}(\widetilde{\mathbf{F}}_K(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}, t), t) = \psi_h^n|_K(\mathbf{F}_K(\widehat{\mathbf{x}})), \quad \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h.$$

142 That is, $\psi_h^n(\mathbf{x})$ and $\psi_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ read the same in the reference element. As a consequence, if $\psi_h^n(\mathbf{x})$ is the
143 i th shape function of V_h , then $\psi_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the i th shape function of $\widetilde{V}_h(t)$. This is the most important
144 property for the numerical discretization of the equations.

Figure 1: Scheme to illustrate the convection of the reference mesh with the velocity field for the case of quadratic elements. Assuming the forward-in-time trajectories of the mesh nodes (gray) are known, new isoparametric, curvilinear elements (green) are constructed. At the same time, the inner points of the elements are convected so that each $\mathbf{x} \in K$ and $\mathbf{X}_h(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \tilde{K}_h(t)$ (red trajectory) share the same natural coordinates $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ in the reference element \hat{K} .

145 The conservative variables ρ , \mathbf{m} and \mathcal{E} are to be approximated by functions belonging to the finite
 146 element space $\tilde{V}_h(t)$. Two numerical approximations are to be considered. The first one, denoted by
 147 $\mathbf{u}_* = [\rho_*, \mathbf{m}_*, \mathcal{E}_*] \in (\tilde{V}_h(t))^4$, is the so-called *non-stabilized solution*, and is obtained by solving Eqs. (4)-
 148 (6) without any kind of stabilization. As it is well known, \mathbf{u}_* may present spurious oscillations due to
 149 the effect of acoustic perturbations [11] or to the presence of discontinuities. The second one, denoted by
 150 $\mathbf{u}_h = [\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h] \in (\tilde{V}_h(t))^4$, is the so-called *stabilized solution*, and is obtained by solving Eqs. (4)-(6)
 151 equipped with some stabilization operators –see Section 2.3. Whenever required (typically at quadrature
 152 points), numerical approximations to v_i and p are computed through the relations

$$v_{i_\square} = \frac{m_{i_\square}}{\rho_\square}, \quad p_\square = (\gamma - 1) \left(\mathcal{E}_\square - \frac{m_{i_\square} m_{i_\square}}{2\rho_\square} \right),$$

153 where the square symbol represents either h or $*$.

154 2.2. Time discretization

155 Let us assume that we dispose of a numerical solution $\mathbf{u}_h^n \in (V_h)^4$ to Eqs. (1)-(3) at a given time t^n , and
 156 that we aim to compute the solution at the next time level t^{n+1} . To do so, we consider a fluid domain such
 157 that $\Omega_f^n \equiv \Omega_h$ and integrate Eqs. (4)-(6) forward-in-time with an implicit–explicit Runge–Kutta method.
 158 The implicit (I) and explicit (E) parts of the method are described by the Butcher tableaux

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc|ccc}
 c^1 = 0 & 0 & & & 0 & & & \\
 c^2 & a_I^{2,1} & a_I^{2,2} & & a_E^{2,1} & & & \\
 c^3 & a_I^{3,1} & a_I^{3,2} & a_I^{3,3} & a_E^{3,1} & a_E^{3,2} & & \\
 \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots & & \ddots & \\
 c^s & a_I^{s,1} & \dots & \dots & a_E^{s,1} & \dots & \dots & a_E^{s,s-1} \\
 \hline
 & b_I^1 & \dots & \dots & b_E^1 & \dots & \dots & b_E^{s-1} \quad b_E^s
 \end{array} \quad (8)$$

159 Note that we consider methods with the same time splitting for both parts.

As usual, the first stage of the Runge–Kutta method is assumed to be equal to the solution at t^n , i.e., $(\cdot)^{[1]} = (\cdot)^n$ for any variable (\cdot) . In addition, we consider $\mathbf{u}_*^{[1]} = \mathbf{u}_h^{[1]}$. Then, for the stages $l = 2, \dots, s$, we set $t^{[l]} = t^{[1]} + \Delta t c^l$, with $\Delta t = t^{n+1} - t^n$, and perform the steps described next.

Step 1 (convect mesh nodes). Each node of the reference mesh \mathbb{T}_h is displaced with the explicit part of the method according to

$$\boldsymbol{\chi}_N^{[l]} = \boldsymbol{\chi}_N^{[1]} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{l-1} a_E^{lk} \mathbf{v}_h^{[k]} \left(\boldsymbol{\chi}_N^{[k]} \right), \quad N = 1, \dots, N_h. \quad (9)$$

As shown in the previous section, the convected nodes define a convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[l]}$, a convected domain $\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}$ and a convected finite element space $\widetilde{V}_h^{[l]} = P_r^{\text{bubble}} \left(\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[l]} \right)$.

Step 2 (compute non-stabilized solution). We employ the explicit part of the method to find a non-stabilized solution $\mathbf{u}_*^{[l]} \in \left(\widetilde{V}_h^{[l]} \right)^4$ such that

$$\left(\rho_*^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} = \left(\rho_h^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}}, \quad (10)$$

$$\left(m_{i*}^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} = \left(m_{ih}^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{l-1} a_E^{lk} f_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (11)$$

$$\left(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_*^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} = \left(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_h^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{l-1} a_E^{lk} f_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (12)$$

for all $\psi_h^{[l]} \in \widetilde{V}_h^{[l]}$, where

$$f_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} := \left(p_h^{[k]}, \frac{\partial \psi_h^{[k]}}{\partial x_i} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} - \left\langle p_h^{[k]} n_i, \psi_h^{[k]} \right\rangle_{\partial \widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (13)$$

$$f_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} := \left(p_h^{[k]} v_j^{[k]}, \frac{\partial \psi_h^{[k]}}{\partial x_j} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} - \left\langle p_h^{[k]} v_j^{[k]} n_j, \psi_h^{[k]} \right\rangle_{\partial \widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}. \quad (14)$$

We recall that, when $\psi_h^{[l]}$ is the i th shape function of $\widetilde{V}_h^{[l]}$, then $\psi_h^{[k]}$ is the i th shape function of $\widetilde{V}_h^{[k]}$. Therefore, when performing the numerical discretization, the terms $f_{m_i}(\dots)$ and $f_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}(\dots)$ can be readily computed by means of the convected meshes $\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}$ and lead to vectors that do not depend on the current Runge–Kutta stage l .

In addition, we are assuming pressure boundary conditions for simplicity, which are imposed weakly through the boundary integral in (13). Normal velocity conditions can be strongly imposed in the momentum equation (11) following the usual procedure –see, e.g. [32]–, although the densities have to be computed first via Eq. (10). Note that, in the case of pressure (resp. normal velocity) boundary conditions, the normal velocities (resp. pressures) have to be computed from the numerical solution in order to evaluate the boundary integral in (14).

Finally, it should be pointed that the left-hand side of the system defined by (10)–(12) is formed by four uncoupled mass matrices, and thus its resolution is straightforward.

Step 3 (compute stabilized solution). The non-stabilized solution $\mathbf{u}_*^{[l]}$ is post-processed to detect spurious oscillations and to compute adequate stabilization operators of artificial-diffusion type –introduced in Section 2.3–, namely

$$\mathcal{S}_\rho \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}, \quad \mathcal{S}_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}, \quad \mathcal{S}_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}.$$

185 We omit the dependence on $\mathbf{u}_*^{[l]}$ in the definitions above for brevity. As we shall see, the operator \mathcal{S}_ρ is
 186 linear with respect to $\rho_h^{[l]}$, whereas \mathcal{S}_{m_i} and $\mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E}$ are nonlinear with respect to $\rho_h^{[l]}$, $\mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}$ and $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}$. Since these
 187 operators are stiff, we now employ the implicit part of the Runge–Kutta method to march in time. More
 188 precisely, we first find $\rho_h^{[l]} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$ such that

$$\left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \Delta t a_I^l \mathcal{S}_\rho \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} = \left(\rho_h^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} - \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{l-1} a_I^k \mathcal{S}_\rho \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad \forall \psi_h^{[l]} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}. \quad (15)$$

189 Then, we find $m_{i_h}^{[l]} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$ and $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$ such that

$$\left(m_{i_h}^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} = b_{m_i}^{[l]}(\psi_h) + \Delta t a_I^l g_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}, \quad (16)$$

$$\left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} = b_\mathcal{E}^{[l]}(\psi_h) + \Delta t a_I^l g_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}, \quad (17)$$

190 for all $\psi_h^{[l]} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$, where

$$b_{m_i}^{[l]}(\psi_h) := \left(m_{i_h}^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{l-1} a_I^k g_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}},$$

$$b_\mathcal{E}^{[l]}(\psi_h) := \left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{l-1} a_I^k g_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}},$$

$$g_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} := f_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} - \mathcal{S}_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (18)$$

$$g_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} := f_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} - \mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}. \quad (19)$$

191 When discretized, Eq. (15) leads to a linear system defined by a positive definite matrix and thus can
 192 readily be solved. However, Eqs. (16)–(17) lead to a coupled nonlinear system since both the left and the
 193 right-hand side terms depend on the unknowns $m_{i_h}^{[l]}$ and $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}$. Its resolution will be detailed in Section 2.4.

194 After Step 3 is finished, we go back to Step 1 if $l < s$. Otherwise, all the internal stages $l = 1, \dots, s$ of the
 195 Runge–Kutta method have been solved and the solution $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1} \in (\tilde{V}_h^{n+1})^4$ at t^{n+1} is computed through

$$\tilde{\chi}_N^{n+1} = \chi_N^{[1]} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^s b_E^k \mathbf{v}_h^{[k]} \left(\chi_N^{[k]}\right), \quad N = 1, \dots, N_h, \quad (20)$$

$$\left(\tilde{\rho}_h^{n+1}, \tilde{\psi}_h^{n+1}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = \left(\rho_h^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} - \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^s b_I^k \mathcal{S}_\rho \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (21)$$

$$\left(\tilde{m}_{i_h}^{n+1}, \tilde{\psi}_h^{n+1}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = \left(m_{i_h}^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^s b_I^k g_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (22)$$

$$\left(\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^{n+1}, \tilde{\psi}_h^{n+1}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = \left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[1]}, \psi_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^s b_I^k g_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}}, \quad (23)$$

196 for all $\tilde{\psi}_h^{n+1} \in \tilde{V}_h^{n+1}$, where the tilde symbol is used to emphasize that the solution is defined at the convected
 197 mesh $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}$. This solution has to be transferred to the reference mesh \mathbb{T}_h in order to proceed again as shown
 198 above and compute the solution at t^{n+2} . To do so, we compute the L^2 projection onto the reference mesh,
 199 that is, we find $\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} \in (V_h)^4$ such that

$$\left(\rho_h^{n+1}, \psi_h\right)_{\Omega_h} = \left(\tilde{\rho}_h^{n+1}, \psi_h\right)_{\Omega_h}, \quad (24)$$

$$\left(m_{i_h}^{n+1}, \psi_h\right)_{\Omega_h} = \left(\tilde{m}_{i_h}^{n+1}, \psi_h\right)_{\Omega_h}, \quad (25)$$

$$\left(\mathcal{E}_h^{n+1}, \psi_h\right)_{\Omega_h} = \left(\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^{n+1}, \psi_h\right)_{\Omega_h}, \quad (26)$$

200 for all $\psi_h \in V_h$.

201 As already discussed in [31, 32] (see also Fig. 2):

- 202 (i) The right-hand side terms in (24)-(26) involve functions defined piecewise in different meshes. Thus,
 203 we approach their computation via high-order quadrature rules [59] and search-locate algorithms [31,
 204 60, 61]. Mesh intersection techniques [62–64] and other remap algorithms [45, 46] could be employed
 205 as well.
- 206 (ii) When there is flow leaving the reference domain, there is a part of Ω_h that lies outside of $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}$. In
 207 those cases, we assume that the solution at $\Omega_h \setminus \tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}$ equals to some known (incoming) flow conditions
 208 $\mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}(\mathbf{x}, t^{n+1})$ in order to solve (24)-(26).
- 209 (iii) If $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1}$ presents discontinuities, \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} may suffer from spurious oscillations. However, these are not large
 210 because the sizes of the elements in $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$ and \mathbb{T}_h are of the same order; hence, if a discontinuity is well
 211 captured with former, it should also be well captured with the latter. In addition, the oscillations that
 212 may appear are to be removed by artificial diffusion when integrating from t^{n+1} to t^{n+2} . Nevertheless,
 213 it is more accurate to take $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1}$ as the solution at t^{n+1} and to consider Eqs. (24)-(26) as the first step
 214 for integrating from t^{n+1} to t^{n+2} rather than the last step for integrating from t^n to t^{n+1} .

Figure 2: Scheme that illustrates the domains and meshes that appear in the formulation. The elements in \mathbb{T}_h are convected forward in time with the flow velocity field to form $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$. The variables ρ_h^{n+1} , m_i^{n+1} , \mathcal{E}_h^{n+1} and ψ_h in Eqs. (24)-(26) are defined piecewise in \mathbb{T}_h , whereas $\tilde{\rho}_h^{n+1}$, \tilde{m}_i^{n+1} and $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^{n+1}$ are defined piecewise in $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$.

215 In the next sections we address the computation of the stabilization operators and the resolution of the
 216 nonlinear system (16)-(17).

217 2.3. Stabilization operators

218 2.3.1. Brenner's model

219 The stabilization operators employed in this work are based on the model developed by Brenner [51] for
 220 compressible and viscous flows. In contrast to the classical Navier–Stokes model, Brenner's model takes into
 221 account for mass diffusion and for the transport of momentum and energy associated with the latter. This
 222 is achieved by replacing the velocity v_i in the convective derivative terms of Navier–Stokes equations by a
 223 *mass velocity*

$$(v_m)_i := v_i - \epsilon \frac{\partial_i \rho}{\rho},$$

with ϵ the mass-diffusion coefficient. Hence, Brenner's model reads

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_t \rho + \partial_j (\rho v_j) &= \partial_j (\epsilon \partial_j \rho), \\ \partial_t m_i + \partial_j (m_i v_j) &= -\partial_i p + \partial_j \sigma_{ij} + \partial_j \left(\epsilon m_i \frac{\partial_j \rho}{\rho} \right), \\ \partial_t \mathcal{E} + \partial_j (\mathcal{E} v_j) &= -\partial_j (p v_j) + \partial_j (v_i \sigma_{ij}) + \partial_j \left(\frac{\kappa}{c_v} \partial_j e \right) + \partial_j \left(\epsilon \mathcal{E} \frac{\partial_j \rho}{\rho} \right),\end{aligned}$$

with $e = p/\rho/(\gamma - 1)$ the specific internal energy, κ the conductivity coefficient, c_v the specific heat for constant volume,

$$\sigma_{ij} = \rho \nu \left[\partial_j v_i + \partial_i v_j - \frac{2}{3} (\partial_k v_k) \delta_{ij} \right]$$

the viscous stress tensor, δ_{ij} the Kronecker delta and ν the kinematic viscosity.

Brenner originally developed his model from physical arguments only. However, its mathematical basis is sound as it has also been derived by Guermond and Popov [54] from purely mathematical arguments, such as the satisfaction of entropy inequalities and the positivity of density and energy – conditions that are not met by the classical Navier–Stokes regularization. The latter authors proved that the most robust regularization corresponds to the case $\kappa/c_v = \rho\epsilon$. In addition, Feireisl and Vasseur [65] have proved the existence of weak solutions to Brenner's model. Finally, Nazarov and Larcher [52] have demonstrated that this model yields better numerical results than the classical Navier–Stokes regularization, which is also in accordance with our own experience.

For ease of implementation, we rewrite Brenner's model as

$$\partial_t \rho + \partial_j (\rho v_j) = \partial_j (\epsilon \partial_j \rho), \quad (27)$$

$$\partial_t m_i + \partial_j (m_i v_j) = -\partial_i p + \partial_j \sigma_{ij}^*, \quad (28)$$

$$\partial_t \mathcal{E} + \partial_j (\mathcal{E} v_j) = -\partial_j (p v_j) + \partial_j q_j^*, \quad (29)$$

with

$$\sigma_{ij}^* = \sigma_{ij}^* (\epsilon, \nu; \mathbf{v}; \nabla \rho, \nabla \mathbf{m}) := \nu [\partial_i m_j - v_j \partial_i \rho + \partial_j m_i - v_i \partial_j \rho] - \frac{2}{3} \nu (\partial_k m_k - v_k \partial_k \rho) \delta_{ij} + \epsilon v_i \partial_j \rho, \quad (30)$$

$$q_j^* = q_j^* (\epsilon, \nu; \mathbf{v}; \nabla \rho, \nabla \mathbf{m}, \nabla \mathcal{E}) := \epsilon [\partial_j \mathcal{E} - v_i \partial_j m_i] + v_i \sigma_{ij}^* (\epsilon, \nu; \mathbf{v}; \nabla \rho, \nabla \mathbf{m}). \quad (31)$$

2.3.2. Discontinuity-capturing operators

The discontinuity capturing (DC) operators aim to stabilize shocks, shear layers and contact discontinuities, and are based on post-processing the non-stabilized solution \mathbf{u}_* as follows.

For simplicity of notation, we drop for the moment the superscript $[k]$ denoting the corresponding stage of the Runge–Kutta method. First, we employ the fine-scale terms $\rho'_h, m'_{i,h}, \mathcal{E}'_h$ to locate the discontinuities. To do so, we define the fluctuation operator $\tilde{\theta}_h := \mathbb{I} - \tilde{L}_h$, with \mathbb{I} the identity and \tilde{L}_h the Lagrange interpolation operator onto the convected mesh $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h$, and the q -average

$$\llbracket u \rrbracket_{q,D} := \left[\int_D u^q \, d\Omega / \int_D \, d\Omega \right]^{1/q}.$$

Then, we compute the quantities

$$e_{\rho,K} = \frac{\llbracket \tilde{\theta}_h \rho_* \rrbracket_{2,K}}{\llbracket \tilde{\rho}_* \rrbracket_{2,\tilde{\Omega}_h}}, \quad e_{m_i,K} = \frac{\llbracket \tilde{\theta}_h m_{i*} \rrbracket_{2,K}}{\sqrt{\llbracket \tilde{\rho}_* \rrbracket_{2,\tilde{\Omega}_h} \llbracket \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_* \rrbracket_{2,\tilde{\Omega}_h}}}, \quad e_{\mathcal{E},K} = \frac{\llbracket \tilde{\theta}_h \mathcal{E}_* \rrbracket_{2,K}}{\llbracket \tilde{\mathcal{E}}_* \rrbracket_{2,\tilde{\Omega}_h}}, \quad e_K = \max \{ e_{\rho,K}, e_{m_i,K}, e_{\mathcal{E},K} \},$$

for each element $K \in \tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h$. Recall that $\tilde{\theta}_h \psi_h = \tilde{\theta}_h \psi'_h \forall \psi_h \in \tilde{V}_h$ according to the multiscale decomposition (7), and that ψ'_h can be seen as a measure of the error in the large-scale term [66]. Hence, e_K is expected to be large at the discontinuities and small at the regions where the solution is smooth.

From e_K , we define the discontinuity sensor

$$S_K := \min \left\{ (r+1)! \left(\frac{C_{\text{DC}}}{r} \right)^{r+1} e_K, 1 \right\}, \quad (32)$$

and the diffusion coefficient

$$\tau_K^{\text{DC}} := \begin{cases} \left[\left(\frac{h_K}{r} \right)^2 \left[\|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_*\|_{1,K} + C_c \llbracket c_* \rrbracket_{2,K} \frac{h_K}{r} \right] S_K, & \text{if } \llbracket \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_* \rrbracket_{1,K} < 0, \\ C_c \llbracket c_* \rrbracket_{2,K} \frac{h_K}{r} S_K, & \text{if } \llbracket \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_* \rrbracket_{1,K} \geq 0, \end{cases}$$

where $h_K = [\int_K d\Omega]^{1/2}$, $c_* = \sqrt{\gamma p_*/\rho_*}$ is the sound speed and C_{DC} and C_c are positive user-defined constants to fine-tune the level of diffusion. Recall that r is the order of the space discretization. The rationale behind Eq. (32) is shown in Appendix A. Then, we perform a linear reconstruction [67] of the τ_K^{DC} 's –defined element-wise– to obtain a continuous, piecewise-linear diffusion coefficient τ_h . More specifically, τ_h^{DC} is defined at each vertex of the mesh as the weighted average of the τ_K 's of the corresponding elements, where the weights are the inverses of the areas of those elements. This is done with the purpose of obtaining smoother results [47, 68]. Furthermore, we set the mass-diffusion coefficient and the kinematic viscosity

$$\epsilon_h^{\text{DC}} = C_\epsilon \tau_h^{\text{DC}}, \quad \nu_h^{\text{DC}} = C_\nu \tau_h^{\text{DC}},$$

where C_ϵ and C_ν are other positive user-defined constants.

Looking back to Brenner's model (27)-(29) and recalling definitions (30)-(31), we finally introduce the DC operators

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_\rho^{\text{DC}}(\rho_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &:= (\epsilon_h^{\text{DC}} \partial_j \rho_h, \partial_j \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}, \\ \mathcal{S}_{m_i}^{\text{DC}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &:= (\sigma_{ij}^* (\epsilon_h^{\text{DC}}, \nu_h^{\text{DC}}; \mathbf{v}_h; \nabla \rho_h, \nabla \mathbf{m}_h), \partial_j \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}, \\ \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}}^{\text{DC}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &:= (q_j^* (\epsilon_h^{\text{DC}}, \nu_h^{\text{DC}}; \mathbf{v}_h; \nabla \rho_h, \nabla \mathbf{m}_h, \nabla \mathcal{E}_h), \partial_j \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}. \end{aligned}$$

2.3.3. Subgrid stabilization

Apart from discontinuities, instabilities may arise also from (initially) small perturbations which propagate through acoustic waves, as demonstrated by Scovazzi [11]. These instabilities can also be seen as a consequence of the presence of nonsymmetric terms in the Galerkin formulation (4)-(6) and of the inexact computation of the integrals in (24)-(26) [59]. Unluckily, the DC operators above are not able to detect and remove these acoustic instabilities, and thus it is necessary to provide another stabilization term.

For that purpose, we extend the subgrid stabilization (SS) technique developed by Guermond et al. for incompressible flows [56] to the present case. In particular, we define

$$\tau_K^{\text{SS}} = C_{\text{SS}} \llbracket c_* \rrbracket_{2,K} \frac{h_K}{r}$$

for each element $K \in \tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h$, perform a linear reconstruction of the τ_K^{SS} 's to obtain τ_h^{SS} , and set

$$\epsilon_h^{\text{SS}} = C_\epsilon \tau_h^{\text{SS}}, \quad \nu_h^{\text{SS}} = C_\nu \tau_h^{\text{SS}}.$$

Then, we add diffusion only in the fine-scale terms, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_\rho^{\text{SS}}(\rho_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &:= (\epsilon_h^{\text{SS}} \partial_j \tilde{\theta}_h \rho_h, \partial_j \tilde{\theta}_h \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}, \\ \mathcal{S}_{m_i}^{\text{SS}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &:= (\sigma_{ij}^* (\epsilon_h^{\text{SS}}, \nu_h^{\text{SS}}; \mathbf{v}_h; \nabla \tilde{\theta}_h \rho_h, \nabla \tilde{\theta}_h \mathbf{m}_h), \partial_j \tilde{\theta}_h \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}, \\ \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}}^{\text{SS}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &:= (q_j^* (\epsilon_h^{\text{SS}}, \nu_h^{\text{SS}}; \mathbf{v}_h; \nabla \tilde{\theta}_h \rho_h, \nabla \tilde{\theta}_h \mathbf{m}_h, \nabla \tilde{\theta}_h \mathcal{E}_h), \partial_j \tilde{\theta}_h \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}. \end{aligned}$$

271 Above, C_ϵ and C_ν are the same as for the DC operators, whereas C_{SS} is another positive user-defined
 272 constant. We have seen in our experiments that the results are not very sensitive with respect to C_{SS} once
 273 stabilization is achieved.

274 The stabilization operators in Eqs. (15), (18)-(19) are hence

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{S}_\rho(\rho_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &= \mathcal{S}_\rho^{\text{DC}}(\rho_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} + \mathcal{S}_\rho^{\text{SS}}(\rho_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}, \\ \mathcal{S}_{m_i}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &= \mathcal{S}_{m_i}^{\text{DC}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} + \mathcal{S}_{m_i}^{\text{SS}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}, \\ \mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} &= \mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E}^{\text{DC}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} + \mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E}^{\text{SS}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h, \psi_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}.\end{aligned}$$

275 *2.4. Resolution of nonlinear system (16)-(17)*

276 To solve nonlinear system (16)-(17), we consider first the following fixed-point iteration: given $m_{i_h}^{[l],k}$,
 277 $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$, find $m_{i_h}^{[l],k+1}$, $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k+1} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}\left(m_{i_h}^{[l],k+1}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \Delta t a_I^l K_{m_i} \left(\mathbf{m}_h^{[l],k+1}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} &= b_{m_i}^{[l]}(\psi_h) + \Delta t a_I^l g_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[l],k}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \\ &\Delta t a_I^l K_{m_i} \left(\mathbf{m}_h^{[l],k}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}},\end{aligned}\quad (33)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k+1}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \Delta t a_I^l K_\mathcal{E} \left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k+1}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} &= b_\mathcal{E}^{[l]}(\psi_h) + \Delta t a_I^l g_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[l]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[l],k+1}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \\ &\Delta t a_I^l K_\mathcal{E} \left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[l],k}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}},\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

278 for all $\psi_h^{[l]} \in \tilde{V}_h^{[l]}$. The equations above are obtained by adding the terms K_{m_1} , K_{m_2} and $K_\mathcal{E}$ to the left and
 279 right-hand sides of Eqs. (16)-(17). These terms are respectively the contributions of ∇m_1 , ∇m_2 and $\nabla \mathcal{E}$ to
 280 \mathcal{S}_{m_1} , \mathcal{S}_{m_2} and $\mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E}$, viz.,

$$\begin{aligned}K_{m_1} \left(\mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} &:= \frac{4}{3} \left(\nu_h^{\text{DC}} \partial_1 m_{1_h}^{[l]}, \partial_1 \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \left(\nu_h^{\text{DC}} \partial_2 m_{1_h}^{[l]}, \partial_2 \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \\ &\frac{4}{3} \left(\nu_h^{\text{SS}} \partial_1 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} m_{1_h}^{[l]}, \partial_1 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \left(\nu_h^{\text{SS}} \partial_2 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} m_{1_h}^{[l]}, \partial_2 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}, \\ K_{m_2} \left(\mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} &:= \left(\nu_h^{\text{DC}} \partial_1 m_{2_h}^{[l]}, \partial_1 \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \frac{4}{3} \left(\nu_h^{\text{DC}} \partial_2 m_{2_h}^{[l]}, \partial_2 \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \\ &\left(\nu_h^{\text{SS}} \partial_1 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} m_{2_h}^{[l]}, \partial_1 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \frac{4}{3} \left(\nu_h^{\text{SS}} \partial_2 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} m_{2_h}^{[l]}, \partial_2 \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}}, \\ K_\mathcal{E} \left(\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}, \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} &:= \left(\epsilon_h^{\text{DC}} \partial_j \mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}, \partial_j \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}} + \left(\epsilon_h^{\text{SS}} \partial_j \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} \mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}, \partial_j \tilde{\theta}_h^{[l]} \psi_h^{[l]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[l]}},\end{aligned}$$

281 and their purpose is to approximately cancel the stiff terms in the right-hand side of the equations so as to
 282 accelerate the convergence rate of the fixed-point iteration and to allow for a larger¹ Δt . Note that these
 283 terms lead to standard stiffness matrices in the numerical implementation, and that the system (33)-(34)
 284 is therefore linear and formed by three uncoupled positive definite matrices. Also note that the energy
 285 equation is solved with the updated momentum.

286 Then, we apply Anderson's acceleration method [69, 70] to the fixed point iteration (33)-(34). This
 287 method is very simple to implement, converges faster than the classical fixed-point iteration –
 288 superlinearly instead of linearly– and is more robust. The iterations are started by assuming that the

¹Recall that the fixed-point iteration $x^{k+1} = g(x^k)$ converges if the eigenvalues of the Jacobian $J(x) := \partial g(x)/\partial x$ are inside the unit circumference in the complex plane. In addition, the convergence speed is governed by the largest modulus eigenvalue. Thus, a stiff right-hand side results in a very slow convergence. Instead, we can consider the fixed point iteration $x^{k+1} + G^k x^{k+1} = g(x^k) + G^k x^k$, with G^k an approximation to $-J(x^k)$, so as to ideally cancel the stiff part in the right-hand side and to obtain a higher convergence rate. Note that the latter iteration is equivalent to the quasi-Newton iteration $x^{k+1} = x^k - [\mathbb{I} + G^k]^{-1} [x^k - g(x^k)]$.

degrees of freedom of $\rho_h^{[l],0}$, $m_{i_h}^{[l],0}$ and $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l],0}$ equal those of $\rho_h^{[l-1]}$, $m_{i_h}^{[l-1]}$ and $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l-1]}$, and are stopped when the relative variation of the L^2 norm of the unknowns is under a prescribed tolerance (10^{-8} or smaller in the case of this work). We remark that, in our experiments, Anderson's acceleration method has considerably reduced the number of required iterations and increased the stability of the scheme in comparison to the classical fixed-point iteration method.

2.5. Summary of the scheme and remarks

The scheme described in previous sections is summarized in Algorithm 1 and will be referred hereafter as the Runge–Kutta forward Lagrange–Galerkin (RK-FLG) scheme.

Algorithm 1: Step from t^n to t^{n+1} of the RK-FLG method.

Data: convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^n$ and solution $\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^n = [\widetilde{\rho}_h^n, \widetilde{\mathbf{m}}_h^n, \widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^n] \in (\widetilde{V}_h^n)^4$ at t^n ; reference mesh \mathbb{T}_h and space V_h ; inflow conditions $\mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$; time step Δt ; Butcher tableaux (8).

- 1 **perform** the L^2 projection of $\widetilde{\rho}_h^n$, $\widetilde{m}_{i_h}^n$ and $\widetilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^n$ onto V_h (Eqs. (24)-(26) with $n+1$ replaced by n) to obtain $\mathbf{u}_h^n = [\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h, \mathcal{E}_h] \in (V_h)^4$,
- 2 **set** $t^{[1]} = t^n$, $\mathbf{u}_*^{[1]} = \mathbf{u}_h^n$, $\mathbf{u}_h^{[1]} = \mathbf{u}_h^n$, $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[1]} = \mathbb{T}_h$,
- 3 **for** $l = 2, \dots, s$ **do**
- 4 **compute** convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[l]}$ from Eq. (9),
- 5 **compute** non-stabilized solution $\mathbf{u}_*^{[l]}$ by solving (10),
- 6 **compute** discontinuity-capturing and subgrid stabilization operators as shown in Section 2.3,
- 7 **compute** stabilized density $\rho_h^{[l]}$ by solving (15),
- 8 **solve** fixed-point iteration (33)-(34) with Anderson's acceleration method [69] to obtain $\mathbf{m}_h^{[l]}$ and $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]}$,
- 9 **end**
- 10 **compute** convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$ and solution $\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1}$ from Eqs. (20)-(23).

Result: $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$, $\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1} \in (\widetilde{V}_h^{n+1})^4$.

The time step is

$$t^{n+1} - t^n = \min_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} \left\{ \text{CFL}_c^n \frac{h_K^{\min}/r}{\|c_h^n\|_{2,K}}, \frac{\text{CFL}_v^n}{\|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h^n\|_{1,K}}, \frac{\text{CFL}_v^n}{\|\nabla \times \mathbf{v}_h^n\|_{1,K}} \right\},$$

where h_K^{\min} is the minimum edge size, whereas CFL_c^n and CFL_v^n are two CFL numbers. Depending on the problem, two strategies are adopted, namely that (S1) the CFL numbers are constant, i.e., $\text{CFL}_\square^n = \text{CFL}_\square$, or that (S2) the CFL numbers increase geometrically at the first time steps, i.e., $\text{CFL}_\square^n = \min\{2\text{CFL}_\square^{n-1}, \text{CFL}_\square\}$, with $\text{CFL}_\square^0 = \text{CFL}_\square/2^{10}$. Here, the square symbol denotes either c or v , and CFL_c and CFL_v are user-defined parameters.

The linear systems to be solved at the different steps are all symmetric, positive definite, and involve only one conservative variable at once. However, for each conservative variable there are two coupled blocks, which appear from the discretization of the large and the fine-scale spaces. The block corresponding to the bubble degrees of freedom is eliminated by static condensation, leading to a linear system for the polynomial degrees of freedom only. This system is solved via the conjugate gradients method with a Jacobi preconditioner.

Next we address some properties of the scheme.

Global conservation. Theoretically, the present method preserves mass, momentum and total energy irrespective of the order of the space and time discretizations, whenever (C1) there is no fluid entering nor leaving the domain Ω_h , (C2) the total force over the domain is null and (C3) no power is introduced through the boundary. In effect, under these conditions,

$$\begin{aligned} f_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, 1 \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} &= - \left\langle p_h^{[k]} n_i, 1 \right\rangle_{\partial \widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0, \\ f_{\mathcal{E}} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, 1 \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} &= - \left\langle p_h^{[k]} v_j^{[k]} n_j, 1 \right\rangle_{\partial \widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

315 for any stage k of the Runge–Kutta method. Furthermore, it can be easily checked that

$$\mathcal{S}_\rho \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, 1 \right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0, \quad \mathcal{S}_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, 1 \right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0, \quad \mathcal{S}_\mathcal{E} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, 1 \right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0.$$

316 Hence, we have from Eqs. (18)-(19), (21)-(23) that

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\rho}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} &= (\rho_h^{[1]}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} = (\rho_h^n, 1)_{\Omega_h}, \\ (\tilde{m}_{i_h}^{n+1}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} &= (m_{i_h}^{[1]}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} = (m_{i_h}^n, 1)_{\Omega_h}, \\ (\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} &= (\mathcal{E}_h^{[1]}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} = (\mathcal{E}_h^n, 1)_{\Omega_h}. \end{aligned}$$

317 On the other hand, since no fluid enters nor leaves the domain, $\tilde{\Omega}_h(t) \equiv \Omega_h \forall t$. Thus, the L^2 projections
318 (24)-(26) and the equations above yield

$$\begin{aligned} (\rho_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} &= (\tilde{\rho}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (\tilde{\rho}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = (\rho_h^n, 1)_{\Omega_h}, \\ (m_{i_h}^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} &= (\tilde{m}_{i_h}^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (\tilde{m}_{i_h}^{n+1}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = (m_{i_h}^n, 1)_{\Omega_h}, \\ (\mathcal{E}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} &= (\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (\tilde{\mathcal{E}}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = (\mathcal{E}_h^n, 1)_{\Omega_h}, \end{aligned}$$

319 q.e.d. In practice, however, conservation [with machine accuracy](#) is not achieved because:

- 320 (i) The linear systems are not solved exactly, but with an iterative method until a prescribed tolerance.
321 Thus, conservation errors cannot be expected to be smaller than the latter. This inconvenience can
322 be circumvented by employing constrained iterative solvers such as [71, 72].
- 323 (ii) It is not possible to impose conditions (C1)-(C3) at the same time. For example, if we impose $p = 0$
324 on the entire boundary, (C2)-(C3) are met, and mass, momentum and total energy are preserved in
325 the moving domain $\tilde{\Omega}_h(t)$. However, due to numerical errors, there is some flux across $\partial\Omega_h$ even if the
326 theoretical solution satisfies $v_i n_i = 0$. Therefore, $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1} \neq \Omega_h$ and there are mass, momentum and energy
327 losses through Eqs. (24)-(26). On the other hand, if we impose $v_i n_i = 0$ at the boundary, conditions
328 (C1) and (C3) are met and hence we could expect conservation of mass and energy. Nevertheless,
329 the total force over the boundary is not numerically zero, even if that is the case for the theoretical
330 solution, and therefore exact momentum conservation cannot be achieved.
- 331 (iii) Even if $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1} \equiv \Omega_h$, the L^2 projections (24)-(26) are not fully conservative when computed via high-
332 order quadrature rules, as is our case. To achieve full conservation, mesh intersection techniques
333 [62–64] or remap algorithms [45, 46] can be employed.

334 Normally, Lagrangian methods are considered *conservative* when they theoretically preserve mass, momen-
335 tum and total energy if conditions (C2)-(C3) are imposed; see, e.g. [6, 10]. It is implicitly understood
336 that conservation cannot be guaranteed from a physical point of view under other conditions, and that the
337 resolution of linear systems and other operations may provoke slight conservation errors. In comparison to
338 conservative Lagrangian methods, the present RK-FLG method additionally requires (C1) and suffers from
339 drawback (iii) above, whose associated conservation errors are still small, but more noticeable. Thus, one
340 can expect the conservation errors of this method to be small, but not close to machine accuracy. To avoid
341 confusions, we shall say that the RK-FLG method is *nearly-conservative*, i.e., conservative only with high
342 accuracy.

343 *Geometric conservation law.* The present scheme also satisfies the so-called discrete geometric conservation
344 law, namely, it preserves uniform solution states, which is of great importance for maintaining nonlinear

345 stability [73, 74]. In effect, if $\mathbf{u}_h^{[k]}$ represents a uniform state $[\rho, \mathbf{m}, \mathcal{E}]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} f_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} &= p \left[\left(1, \frac{\partial \psi_h^{[k]}}{\partial x_i} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} - \langle n_i, \psi_h^{[k]} \rangle_{\partial \widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} \right] = 0, \\ f_{\mathcal{E}} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} &= pv_j \left[\left(1, \frac{\partial \psi_h^{[k]}}{\partial x_j} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} - \langle n_j, \psi_h^{[k]} \rangle_{\partial \widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} \right] = 0, \end{aligned}$$

346 and

$$\mathcal{S}_\rho \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0, \quad \mathcal{S}_{m_i} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0, \quad \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}} \left(\rho_h^{[k]}, \mathbf{m}_h^{[k]}, \mathcal{E}_h^{[k]}, \psi_h^{[k]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[k]}} = 0,$$

347 for all $\psi_h^{[k]} \in \widetilde{V}_h^{[k]}$. Also, if $\mathbf{u}_h^{[1]}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_h^{[l-1]}$ represent uniform states, by virtue of (9), the mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[l]}$ is just
348 a translation of the mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[1]}$ and therefore $\left(1, \psi_h^{[l]} \right)_{\Omega_h^{[l]}} = \left(1, \psi_h^{[1]} \right)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}}$. Looking back at Eqs. (15)-(17)

349 and taking into account the relations above, it is easy to check that $\mathbf{u}_h^{[l]}$ is also uniform state solution, i.e.,
350 $\rho_h^{[l]} = \rho$, $m_{i_h}^{[l]} = m_i$, $\mathcal{E}_h^{[l]} = \mathcal{E}$. Hence, it is deduced that $\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1}$ is a uniform state solution if so is \mathbf{u}_h^n . Since
351 $\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}_h^{n+1}$ is smooth, the L^2 projection (24)-(26) can be computed exactly, even though $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1} \neq \mathbb{T}_h$, and thus \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}
352 is also a uniform state solution, q.e.d.

353 *Local conservation.* Since we employ a continuous Galerkin discretization, the scheme is locally conservative,
354 as pointed by Hughes et al. [75]. In addition, it can be written as a residual distribution method [18, 19],
355 which also guarantees local conservation and, under some reasonable assumptions such as stability and
356 consistency of the scheme, convergence of the numerical solution to a weak solution of the Brenner's equations
357 (recall that these are the equations we are actually solving, since we employ artificial viscosity). At the same
358 time, Brenner's regularization ensures positivity of pressure and density and satisfies entropy principles [54],
359 so we can assume that the weak solution of the viscous model converges to a weak dissipative solution of
360 the Euler equations when the diffusion parameters $\epsilon, \nu \rightarrow 0$. Since this is automatically satisfied when the
361 mesh size $h \rightarrow 0$, we can expect that our method converges to a weak dissipative solution [76] of the Euler
362 equations.

363 3. Numerical experiments

364 In this section, we test the RK-FLG method against several canonical examples in the literature to
365 analyze its performance. For this purpose, we introduce the L^1 error indicator

$$e_1 := \frac{\|\rho_h - \rho\|_{1, \Omega_h}}{\|\rho\|_{1, \Omega_h}} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\|m_{ih} - m_i\|_{1, \Omega_h}}{\sqrt{\|\rho\|_{1, \Omega_h}} \|\mathcal{E}\|_{1, \Omega_h}} + \frac{\|\mathcal{E}_h - \mathcal{E}\|_{1, \Omega_h}}{\|\mathcal{E}\|_{1, \Omega_h}},$$

366 where $\|u\|_{1, \Omega_h} := \int_{\Omega_h} |u| d\Omega$ denotes the usual L^1 norm. Also, we introduce the conservation errors

$$e_\rho := \left| \frac{\llbracket \rho_h - \rho_h^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}}{\llbracket \rho_h^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}} \right|, \quad e_{m_i} := \left| \frac{\llbracket m_{ih} - m_{ih}^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}}{\sqrt{\llbracket \rho_h^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}} \llbracket \mathcal{E}_h^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}} \right|, \quad e_{\mathcal{E}} := \left| \frac{\llbracket \mathcal{E}_h - \mathcal{E}_h^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}}{\llbracket \mathcal{E}_h^0 \rrbracket_{1, \Omega_h}} \right|.$$

367 for those problems in which either mass, momentum or energy are preserved. Here, the variables without
368 superscript are assumed to be evaluated at the final time T . The mesh size is defined as $h := \sqrt{4|\Omega_h|/\sqrt{3}N_E}$,
369 with $|\Omega_h| = \int_{\Omega_h} d\Omega$ and N_E the number of elements; that is, if all the elements were equilateral triangles of
370 the same size, h would represent the edge size of those.

371 In all tests, we set

$$C_{SS} = 100, \quad C_{DC} = 5, \quad C_c = 0.1, \quad C_\epsilon = 10, \quad C_\nu = 5, \quad CFL_c = 1, \quad CFL_\nu = 0.30,$$

372 unless specified otherwise. In addition, the reference meshes were generated with BAMG software [77],
 373 space discretizations up to fifth-order were considered and the fourth-order ARK4(3)7L[2]SA1 Runge–Kutta
 374 method of Kennedy and Carpenter [78] was employed to march in time. The integrals in the formulation
 375 are computed via the quadrature rules detailed in Table 1. We employ one set of rules for Eqs. (24)–(26)
 376 and another set for the rest of integrals. The codes were implemented in Julia language [79].

Table 1: Number of nodes, degree of accuracy and reference of the employed quadrature rules.

	$r = 1$	$r = 2$	$r = 3$	$r = 4$	$r = 5$
Integrals in (24)–(26)	25, 10, [80]	88, 20, [81]	175, 30, [82]	175, 30, [82]	175, 30, [82]
Rest of integrals	16, 8 [80]	42, 14, [80]	88, 20, [81]	88, 20, [81]	175, 30, [82]

377 Discontinuous initial conditions are regularized by using functions of the form $H_h(x) := 0.5 + 0.5 \tanh(x/(2h/r))$
 378 instead of unit step functions. In addition, the initial conditions of some tests such as the Shu–Osher tube
 379 and the shock–vortex interaction consist on the superposition of a shock wave with a given fluid field. How-
 380 ever, it is very difficult to provide an initial condition that matches exactly the numerical solution for a
 381 shock wave, and hence some small wiggles may appear and spoil the solution –see, e.g., [52, Fig. 1]. As a
 382 remedy, we first simulate a (steady or traveling) shock wave and save the solution when those wiggles are
 383 away from the shock. Then, we employ the numerical solution at the shock (as well as the given incremental
 384 fluid field) to define the initial condition of those tests.

385 3.1. Acoustic wave propagation

386 As initial benchmark, we consider the simple case of the one-dimensional propagation of an acoustic
 387 wave. This is done to prove the effect of the SS and to compute the maximum CFL_c number at which the
 388 method can run without becoming unstable. Following [10, 11], we consider the initial conditions

$$\rho^0 = 1 + \omega, \quad p^0 = 1 + \omega, \quad v_1^0 = \omega, \quad v_2^0 = 0,$$

389 with

$$\omega = \begin{cases} 0.01 \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi (x_1 - 0.25)}{0.25} \right) \right], & 0.25 < x_1 < 0.50, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

390 The domain is the rectangle $[0, 1] \times [0, 0.1]$, $\gamma = 7/5$, we impose $v_i n_i = 0$ on the entire boundary, the final
 391 time is $T = 0.3$ and strategy (S1) is employed.

392 Fig. 3 shows the solution for fifth-order elements and (i) no SS and no DC, (ii) no SS and DC, (iii) SS
 393 and no DC, and (iv) SS and DC. As can be seen, in the case (i), the solution turns unstable when $t = 0.04$.
 394 In the case (ii), the method runs until $t = T$, although the solution presents many oscillations and is smeared
 395 at the peaks. However, in the cases (iii) and (iv), the solutions are coincident, smooth and compare very
 396 well with those of [10, 11, 16]. Hence, the SS is necessary even if the DC operators are active, as already
 397 pointed by [11] in the context of variational multiscale methods. Also note that the DC operators do not
 398 smear the solution if the SS is applied. On the other hand, Table 2 shows the maximum CFL_c number at
 399 which the method can run without suffering from acoustic instabilities.

Figure 3: Numerical solution of the acoustic wave test at time t for $r = 5$, $h/r \simeq 0.0075$ and $\text{CFL}_c = 1.45$. Legend: (—) no SS and no DC, (—) no SS and DC, (—) SS and no DC, (—) SS and DC.

Table 2: Maximum CFL_c number for acoustic stability.

r	1	2	3	4	5
CFL_c^{\max}	3.10	2.20	1.90	1.70	1.45

3.2. Sod tube

Next we run the classical Sod tube test to assess the ability of the method to capture planar waves. The initial condition is given by

$$\rho^0, p^0 = \begin{cases} 1, & 1, & \text{if } x_1 \leq 0.5, \\ 0.125, & 0.1, & \text{if } x_1 > 0.5, \end{cases}$$

and $v_1^0 = v_2^0 = 0$. The domain is the rectangle $[0, 1] \times [0, 0.1]$, $\gamma = 7/5$, $v_i n_i = 0$ is imposed at each boundary, strategy (S1) is employed and $T = 0.2$. The theoretical solution is obtained from [83]. To demonstrate the robustness of the method, we consider meshes that are somehow irregular and with edges that are not aligned with the x_2 direction, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Mesh of size $h \simeq 0.0375$ employed in the Sod test.

As can be seen in Fig. 5, as the mesh is refined, the shock wave, the contact discontinuity and the expansion wave are captured without oscillations and within the same planes. In addition, the method is able to keep constant the velocity and the pressure across the contact discontinuity despite these are not the discretization variables. For brevity, we only show the results for $r = 5$ as those for lower-order discretizations are almost identical whenever h/r remains the same. The figure also shows the results for a WENO5 scheme² [84]. It can be checked that our method is slightly more dissipative at the expansion wave and at the contact discontinuity, whereas the shock wave is captured similarly.

²Note that, in finite volume methods, the distance between nodes is h , and not h/r as in finite element methods.

Figure 5: Numerical solution of the Sod test at $t = 0.2$ for $r = 5$.

414 In addition, Fig. 6 shows the behavior of the L^1 error and of the conservation errors in mass and energy
 415 with respect to the mesh discretization. It can be checked that the L^1 error does not depend sensitively
 416 with r and converges as $\mathcal{O}(h/r)$, as expected. The conservation errors vary from 10^{-8} to 10^{-5} , and are one
 417 order of magnitude smaller for $r \geq 3$.

Figure 6: Numerical errors in the Sod test.

418 3.3. Shu–Osher tube

419 The Shu–Osher tube test [85] is given by the initial conditions

$$\rho^0, v_1^0, v_2^0, p^0 = \begin{cases} 3.857143, & 2.629369, & 0 & 10.33333, & \text{if } x_1 < -4, \\ 1 + \lambda \sin(5x_1), & 0, & 0, & 1, & \text{if } x_1 \geq -4, \end{cases}$$

420 with $\lambda = 0.2$, in the domain $[-5, 5] \times [-0.5, 0.5]$. Note that $\lambda = 0$ corresponds to the case of a Mach 3 shock
 421 wave moving to the right. Normal velocity conditions are imposed on the entire boundary, $\gamma = 7/5$, the final
 422 time is $T = 1.8$ and strategy (S1) is employed.

423 The reference solution of this test has a very complex structure in the density, and thus it is usually
 424 employed to demonstrate the advantages of using high-order space discretizations. However, as shown in
 425 Fig. 7, in our case we obtain similar results for different r whenever h/r –or the number of nodes– remains
 426 similar. Indeed, linear elements seem to be a little less dissipative. The latter is due to the fact that the
 427 discontinuity sensor is defined element-wise; thus, for high-order elements the artificial viscosity acts on a
 428 wider region and smears more the post-shock oscillations. In the figure, we also plot the results obtained
 429 with a second-order MUSCL code [84] and with a WENO5 finite volume scheme [84] for a similar number
 430 of degrees of freedom in the x_1 direction. As can be seen, our method yields better results than the MUSCL
 431 method, although it is again more dissipative than the WENO5 scheme. Nevertheless, the structure of the
 432 post-shock oscillations is well captured and the results seem to converge to the reference solution when the
 433 mesh is refined. Also note that our results for $r = 1$ look qualitatively more similar to those of WENO5
 434 scheme than to those of MUSCLE method; therefore, we can say that in our case low and high-order
 435 elements yield similar results not because of a poor performance of high-order elements, but because of a
 436 good performance of low-order ones.

Figure 7: Numerical solution of the Shu–Osher test at $t = 1.8$ at the full domain (left) and at the region $0.5 \leq x_1 \leq 2.5$ (right). The reference solution corresponds to the WENO5 scheme for $h = 0.003125$.

437 *3.4. Two-dimensional Noh implosion*

438 The two-dimensional Noh implosion [86] is a classical benchmark used to check the preservation of
 439 symmetry in radial shocks. It is defined by an ideal gas with $\gamma = 5/3$ and initial conditions

$$\rho^0 = 1, \quad v_i^0 = -\frac{x_i}{|\mathbf{x}|}, \quad p^0 = 0.$$

440 To avoid numerical problems, the initial pressure is set to $p^0 = 10^{-9}$. The theoretical solution is a shock
 441 which propagates radially outwards with a velocity $1/3$, viz.,

$$\rho, v_i, p = \begin{cases} 16, & 0, & \frac{16}{3}, & \text{if } |\mathbf{x}| \leq t/3, \\ 1 + \frac{t}{|\mathbf{x}|}, & -\frac{x_i}{|\mathbf{x}|}, & 0, & \text{if } |\mathbf{x}| > t/3. \end{cases}$$

442 We consider two versions of this test. In the first one, the equations are solved in the domain $[0, 0.4]^2$
 443 with a uniform mesh, with zero pressure conditions on the right and upper boundaries and non-penetration
 444 conditions –i.e., $v_i n_i = 0$ – on the left and bottom boundaries. In the second one, the equations are solved
 445 in the domain $[-0.4, 0.4]^2$ with a non-uniform mesh defined approximately by $N \times 2N$ elements in the first
 446 quadrant, $2N \times 2N$ elements in the second quadrant, $2N \times N$ elements in the third quadrant and $N \times N$
 447 elements in the fourth quadrant, with N a given parameter. In this case, zero pressure boundary conditions
 448 are imposed on the entire boundary. The final time is $T = 0.6$ and strategy (S2) is employed. **It should be**
 449 **pointed that some finite volume and finite differences methods, including WENO schemes, fail to solve this**
 450 **problem as they develop instabilities in the cold gas region [87, 88].**

451 Fig. 8 shows the solution for fifth-order elements. As can be seen, radial symmetry is preserved very well
 452 in the case of uniform meshes. In the case of non-uniform meshes, the numerical solution loses symmetry
 453 at the center of the domain; e.g., the velocity is no longer zero at this region. However, radial symmetry is
 454 still preserved at the shock, as can also be seen in Fig. 9. This is in accordance with other references [6, 13].
 455 For brevity, the results for $r < 5$ are not shown, although they are nearly identical whenever h/r remains
 456 similar. The large error in the densities at the center of the domain –both for uniform and non-uniform
 457 meshes– is a common pathology known as wall-heating problem [86].

458 On the other hand, Fig. 10 shows an example of non-uniform mesh and the values of the discontinuity
 459 sensor at each element. It can be checked that the sensor is active only at the elements closest to the shock.
 460 Finally, it is seen in Fig. 11 that the L^1 error indicator behaves as $\mathcal{O}(h/r)$ and does not depend sensitively
 461 on r . Note that this error is only slightly higher for non-uniform meshes.

Figure 8: Numerical solution of the Noh test at $t = 0.6$ in the domain $[0, 0.4]^2$ (left) and in the domain $[-0.4, 0.4]^2$ (right) for $r = 5$.

Figure 9: Numerical solution of the Noh test at $t = 0.6$ in the domain $[-0.4, 0.4]^2$ for $r = 5$ and $h/r \approx 0.0043$.

Figure 10: Mesh (left), discontinuity sensor (middle) and detail of the mesh and the discontinuity sensor at the second quadrant (right) in the Noh test for $r = 5$ and $h/r \approx 0.0043$.

Figure 11: L^1 errors in the Noh test for uniform (left) and non-uniform (right) meshes.

462 3.5. Two-dimensional Sedov explosion

463 The Sedov explosion is another classical test with radial symmetry. Initially, $\rho^0 = 1$, $v_i^0 = 0$ and the
 464 internal energy is zero everywhere except at the origin, where there is a delta source such that the total
 465 energy is $E_{\text{total}} \approx 0.98404$. To avoid numerical problems, this initial energy field is regularized as

$$\mathcal{E}^0 = \begin{cases} \frac{10^{-9}}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{\pi E^{\text{total}}}{(\pi^2 - 4)\delta^2} \left[1 + \cos\left(\frac{\pi|\mathbf{x}|}{\delta}\right) \right], & \text{if } |\mathbf{x}| \leq \delta, \\ \frac{10^{-9}}{\gamma - 1}, & \text{if } |\mathbf{x}| > \delta, \end{cases}, \quad \delta = 4\frac{h}{r}.$$

466 This source of energy is transformed into kinetic energy through a shock wave which propagates radially
 467 outward. The theoretical solution can be estimated as shown in [89]. The same two versions as in the Noh
 468 test are considered –i.e., the same kind of meshes and the same boundary conditions–, although here the
 469 domains are respectively $[0, 1.2]^2$ and $[-1.2, 1.2]^2$. We march in time with strategy (S2) until $T = 1.0$ and
 470 the adiabatic constant is $\gamma = 7/5$.

471 Figs. 12 and 13 show the solutions for fifth-order elements –again, the solutions for $r < 5$ are nearly
 472 identical and thus are not shown for brevity. The numerical solution of the WENO5 scheme [84] for the
 473 first version of the test is also plotted. As with Noh test, radial symmetry is preserved very well in the case
 474 of uniform meshes, and with reasonable accuracy in the case of non-uniform ones. In both cases, there are
 475 some slight oscillations before the shock, although they diminish as the mesh is refined. The maximum value
 476 for the density is very sensitive to h/r , and thus is somehow far from its theoretical value for the considered
 477 mesh sizes. Nevertheless, the results for this variable are very similar to those of WENO5 scheme, and it

478 is clear that finer meshes or anisotropic mesh refinement techniques would provide a more accurate result.
479 Also note that in our method the velocity near the origin does not suffer from spurious oscillations. This is
480 a pathology present in many methods, such as some WENO schemes –as shown in Fig. 12 and also in [87]–,
481 which stems from the numerical divisions into a near-zero density –see also the comparison made by [90] for
482 different methods. Finally, it can be checked that the discontinuity sensor is active only at the shock.

Figure 12: Numerical solution of the Sedov test at $t = 1$ in the domain $[0, 1.2]^2$ (left) and in the domain $[-1.2, 1.2]^2$ (right) for $r = 5$.

Figure 13: Numerical solution of the Sedov test at $t = 1$ in the domain $[-1.2, 1.2]^2$ for $r = 5$ and $h/r \approx 0.0128$.

483 Furthermore, Fig. 14 shows the errors in the conservation of mass, momentum and energy for the case
 484 of non-uniform meshes. As can be seen, the errors are considerably higher for linear elements, whereas for
 485 $r \geq 2$ the results are of the same order of magnitude.

Figure 14: Conservation errors in Sedov test with non-uniform meshes.

486 3.6. Single-material triple-point problem

487 In this test, the rectangular domain $[-1, 6] \times [-1.5, 1.5]$ is filled with a gas of constant $\gamma = 7/5$ at the three
 488 different states shown in Fig. 15. The gas is initially at rest in all the domain. Non-penetration conditions
 489 are imposed on the entire boundary and time-marching strategy (S1) is employed until $T = 5$.

Figure 15: Initial conditions for the single-material triple-point test.

490 Fig. 16 shows the numerical solution for $h/r \simeq 0.027$. The results are nearly identical for first and
 491 fifth-order elements. The only differences are seen at the vortex, which is slightly thinner in the case $r = 5$,
 492 and at the Kelvin–Helmholtz instabilities in the horizontal contact discontinuity, which are slightly more
 493 visible for $r = 5$. The solution is very good agreement with [45, 91].

Figure 16: Numerical solution of the single-material, triple-point test at $t = 5$ for $h/r \approx 0.027$.

494 In addition, Table 3 shows the errors in mass and energy conservation for $h \approx 0.027$ and $r \leq 5$. As can
 495 be seen, they vary from $\mathcal{O}(10^{-5})$ to $\mathcal{O}(10^{-8})$ and are slightly smaller for high-order elements.

Table 3: Errors in the conservation of mass and energy for the single-material triple-point test and for $h/r \approx 0.027$.

	$r = 1$	$r = 2$	$r = 3$	$r = 4$	$r = 5$
e_ρ	8.824E-05	3.169E-06	1.128E-07	8.785E-08	1.137E-06
$e_\mathcal{E}$	8.207E-05	5.247E-06	1.192E-08	2.628E-07	4.987E-07

496 3.7. Rayleigh–Taylor instability

497 In this test, a gas of density $\rho^0 = 2$ rests on top of a lighter gas of density $\rho^0 = 1$ in static equilibrium
 498 under the presence of a gravitational field. The domain is the rectangle $[0, 0.125] \times [-0.5, 0.5]$, the interface
 499 between the fluids is placed at $x_2 = 0$, $\gamma = 5/3$ for both gases, the gravitational acceleration is $g = 1$ and the
 500 initial pressure is hydrostatic, with $p^0(x_2 = 0.5) = 1$. The equilibrium is broken by a perturbation in the
 501 velocity field of the form

$$v_1^0 = 0, \quad v_2^0 = 0.03 [\exp(-2\pi x_2^2) - \exp(\pi/2)] \cos(8\pi x_1).$$

502 Non-penetration boundary conditions are applied on the entire boundary and strategy (S1) is employed to
 503 march in time until $T = 1.95$.

504 Figure 17 shows the results for several values of h/r and r . As can be seen, the (physically admissible)
 505 Kelvin–Helmholtz instabilities are more visible as the mesh is refined, as expected [92]. The value of r does
 506 not affect sensitively to the results, although it could be said that higher r leads to slightly more vortical
 507 solutions. The results compare well to those of [93].

Figure 17: Density field in the Rayleigh–Taylor instability at $t = 1.95$. For visualization purposes, we plot the solution only at the subdomain $[0, 0.125] \times [-0.25, 0.25]$.

508 On the other hand, Table 4 shows the mass conservation errors for the considered space discretizations.
 509 In this case, these are significantly larger for first-order elements, whereas for $r \geq 2$ they are of the order of
 510 10^{-7} and 10^{-8} .

Table 4: Mass conservation errors, e_ρ , in the Rayleigh–Taylor instability.

	$r = 1$	$r = 2$	$r = 3$	$r = 4$	$r = 5$
$h/r \simeq 0.0027$	2.760E-05	9.091E-08	9.874E-08	3.160E-07	1.307E-07
$h/r \simeq 0.0018$	2.278E-05	3.368E-07	7.500E-08	2.293E-07	1.028E-08
$h/r \simeq 0.0011$	2.337E-05	2.171E-07	9.300E-08	1.289E-07	6.026E-08

511 3.8. Shock–vortex interaction

512 This test considers the interaction between a steady planar shock wave and a rotating vortex [94] in the
 513 domain $[0, 2] \times [0, 1]$. In particular, the shock is placed at $x_1 = 0.5$ and is defined by the upstream conditions
 514 $p_\infty = 1$, $\rho_\infty = 1$ and $\mathbf{v}_\infty = [1.5c_\infty, 0]$. On the other hand, the vortex is initially centered at $(0.25, 0.5)$ and is
 515 of radius $b = 0.175$. The velocity field inside the latter is given by $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_\infty + v_\theta \mathbf{e}_\theta$, where

$$v_\theta = \begin{cases} v_m \frac{r}{a}, & \text{if } r \leq a, \\ v_m \frac{a}{a^2 - b^2} \left(r - \frac{b^2}{r} \right), & \text{if } a < r \leq b, \end{cases}$$

516 r is the distance to the vortex center, \mathbf{e}_θ is the unit vector along the counter-clockwise azimuthal direction
 517 (around the vortex center), $a = 0.075$ is a constant, and $v_m = 0.9c_\infty$ is the maximum tangential velocity of
 518 the vortex. The internal energy and the density inside the vortex are obtained from

$$e = e_\infty - \frac{1}{\gamma} \int_r^b \frac{v_\theta(r')^2}{r'} dr', \quad \rho = \rho_\infty \left(\frac{e}{e_\infty} \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma-1}}.$$

519 The adiabatic constant is $\gamma = 7/5$ and the initial conditions downstream the shock are determined by the
 520 well-known Rankine–Hugoniot relations. Normal velocity boundary conditions are imposed on the entire
 521 boundary and time-marching strategy (S1) is employed until the final time $T = 0.7$.

522 Fig. 18 shows the solution for $r = 5$ and $h/r \simeq 0.0021$. As can be seen, the vortex moves downstream
 523 and crosses the shock. Then, the shock is slightly distorted and the vortex is compressed into an elliptical

524 shape, eventually breaking into two separated vortices. In addition, a complex structure of acoustic waves
 525 develops after the shock front. The results compare very well with those of [68, 94–96].

Figure 18: Numerical solution of the shock–vortex interaction problem for $r = 5$ and $h/r \approx 0.0021$.

526 3.9. Taylor–Green vortex

527 As final benchmark, we solve the Taylor–Green vortex problem to check if the method performs well
 528 when the solution is smooth. This test is defined by the initial conditions

$$\rho^0 = 1, \quad v_1^0 = \sin(\pi x_1) \cos(\pi x_2), \quad v_2^0 = -\cos(\pi x_1) \sin(\pi x_2), \quad p^0 = 1 + 0.25 [\cos(2\pi x_1) + \cos(2\pi x_2)],$$

529 and a constant-in-time heat source per unit of volume

$$Q = \frac{3\pi}{8} [\cos(3\pi x_1) \cos(\pi x_2) - \cos(\pi x_1) \cos(3\pi x_2)].$$

530 The domain is the square $[0, 1]^2$, non-penetration boundary conditions are prescribed on the entire boundary
 531 and $\gamma = 5/3$. The test is run up to $T = 0.5$ with strategy (S1). The exact solution is $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \rho^0(\mathbf{x})$,
 532 $m_i(\mathbf{x}, t) = m_i^0(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathcal{E}^0(\mathbf{x})$; see Fig. 19.

Figure 19: Numerical solution of the Taylor–Green test at $t = 0.5$ for $r = 5$ and $h/r \simeq 0.020$.

533 As shown in Fig. 20, the L^1 errors are smaller and converge much faster with h/r for higher-order
 534 elements, as expected. It is also seen that these errors are slightly larger when the DC operators are applied,
 535 although the convergence rate –shown in Table 5– is still very good. On the other hand, the conservation
 536 errors in mass and energy are nearly identical with and without DC, whereas the momentum conservation
 537 errors are slightly larger with DC. In contrast with previous tests, here fifth-order elements clearly yield
 538 smaller conservation errors.

Figure 20: Numerical errors in Taylor–Green test without DC (dashed lines) and with DC (solid lines).

Table 5: Mean convergence rate of the e_1 error with respect to h/r in the Taylor–Green test.

	$r=1$	$r=2$	$r=3$	$r=4$	$r=5$
Without DC	1.94	2.51	3.81	4.54	5.65
With DC	2.57	3.28	4.26	5.47	6.51

539 3.10. Profiling times

540 Next we address the computer times required to solve some of the experiments above in a 64-core AMD
541 Epyc 7601 CPU 2.20 GHz machine with 260GB of RAM (one experiment per core). For instance, Table 6
542 shows the total CPU time per simulated instant for the case of the Noh test with non-uniform meshes, as well
543 as the time devoted per simulated instant to the resolution of the linear systems and to the computation of

544 the f and g terms defined in Eqs. (13)-(14) and (18)-(19), which result to be by far the two most expensive
 545 tasks. Note that each simulated instant requires the resolution of seven internal stages for the considered
 546 ARK4(3)7L[2]SA1 Runge–Kutta scheme [78]. As can be seen, for the same number of nodes, the resolution
 547 of the linear systems is less expensive for low-order elements, as the matrices are more sparse, whereas the
 548 computation of the f and g terms is less expensive for high-order elements, as the total number of quadrature
 549 nodes in the mesh (proportional to the number of elements and to number of quadrature nodes per element
 550 detailed in Table 1) is smaller. As a consequence, the total time does not result to be very sensitive to r
 551 whenever the number of nodes remains the same. Also note that the algorithm complexity is approximately
 552 1.5 irrespective of r , and that the number of iterations in the Anderson method increases with r , but remains
 553 constant with h/r .

Table 6: Profiling times (in seconds) per simulated instant for the RK-FLG scheme in the Noh test.

r	h/r	Elements	Nodes	Mean nb. of Anderson iterations	Total	Rate w.r.t. nb. of nodes	Resolution of linear systems	Computation of f and g terms
1	0.0117	10782	5524	36.06	10.30	-	0.69	7.75
1	0.0075	25716	13063	35.25	28.09	1.59	1.80	21.79
1	0.0048	62650	31644	34.49	76.08	1.59	5.31	58.31
2	0.0106	3200	6545	40.07	10.42	-	1.43	6.72
2	0.0071	7216	14649	42.18	27.08	1.64	3.45	18.40
2	0.0046	17468	35273	44.04	66.40	1.46	9.43	45.51
3	0.0105	1450	6670	48.69	13.46	-	1.87	8.36
3	0.0071	3200	14617	50.53	31.24	1.51	5.02	19.61
3	0.0047	7216	32797	50.09	74.57	1.56	12.04	47.72
4	0.0104	826	6753	56.26	10.66	-	2.76	4.90
4	0.0064	2256	18289	58.09	36.15	1.68	9.10	18.40
4	0.0043	5030	40601	57.51	79.18	1.45	20.32	40.46
5	0.0102	570	7276	64.02	14.92	-	4.24	6.63
5	0.0064	1450	18366	64.10	46.74	1.68	12.94	23.68
5	0.0043	3200	40361	62.97	99.57	1.43	28.89	49.33

554 In addition, Fig. 21 shows the relation between the L^1 error and the total CPU time. It is seen that,
 555 for discontinuous solutions, the performance is approximately the same for low and high-order elements.
 556 This is due to the fact that similar values of h/r lead both to similar CPU times and to similar L^1 errors,
 557 as discussed previously. However, for smooth solutions, similar values of h/r lead to smaller L^1 errors for
 558 high-order elements and to similar CPU times. Thus, high-order elements perform much better in this case.

Figure 21: L^1 errors versus the total CPU time (in seconds) for the Noh test with non-uniform mesh (left) and for the Taylor–Green test (right) with DC (solid lines) and without DC (dashed lines).

4. Conclusions

In this work, we present a novel Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of compressible and inviscid flows. As main contributions, the method considers high-order continuous space discretizations on unstructured triangular meshes and is (nearly) conservative irrespective of the order of the time-marching algorithm. Acoustic instabilities are killed via subgrid stabilization techniques, whereas discontinuities are first detected from the values of the fine-scale terms of a previously computed non-stabilized solution, and are then captured via artificial diffusion. Both the subgrid stabilization and the discontinuity capturing operators are based on Brenner’s model [51] for compressible and viscous flows.

The scheme has been tested on several benchmark problems using up to fifth-order elements and a fourth-order Runge–Kutta method. As expected, numerical experiments show that, for the same number of nodes, high-order elements provide much smaller L^1 errors than low-order elements when the solution is smooth, and similar L^1 errors when the solution is discontinuous. In addition, high-order elements present smaller conservation errors and require approximately the same CPU time.

The method marches in time with an implicit–explicit Runge–Kutta scheme. Thus, a non-linear system of equations has to be solved at each stage, which is accomplished by means of a simple, fixed-point iteration accelerated via Anderson’s method [69]. Although the number of required iterations is not very high, avoiding the resolution of this nonlinear system could clearly improve the efficiency of the method. For that purpose, Rosenbrock–Wanner methods [97–99] or LIRK-W methods [100], which require only the resolution of an implicit linear system at each stage, could be implemented. Other works which could be addressed in the future are the implementation of anisotropic mesh refinement techniques [44, 101–105] and of alternative remapping techniques [45, 46], the enforcement of exact conservation via constrained iterative solvers [71, 72] and the extension of the method to three-dimensional and/or large-scale computations.

Acknowledgements

This research has been partially funded by project PGC-2018-097565-BI00 from the “Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades” of Spain and the European Regional Development Fund, and by the FPU16/05509 grant to M. Colera from the “Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades” of Spain. The authors acknowledge Professors J.L. Prieto, P. Galán del Sastre, L. Saavedra and L. Sanz for many kind and helpful discussions, as well as two anonymous referees for their insightful comments.

Appendix A. Derivation of formula (32)

Let $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ be a continuous variable. We define at each element K a characteristic length l_K such that

$$\max_{i=0,\dots,r+1} \left| \frac{\partial^{r+1} u}{\partial x_1^{r+1-i} \partial x_2^i} \right|_K = \frac{\llbracket u \rrbracket_{2,\Omega}}{l_K^{r+1}}.$$

That is, l_K represents a length scale associated with the local variations in u . If u_h is the finite element approximation to u , from approximation theory and the fact that $\llbracket v \rrbracket_{2,K} \leq \|v\|_{\infty,K}$, we have that the error satisfies

$$e_{u,K} := \frac{\llbracket u - u_h \rrbracket_{2,K}}{\llbracket u \rrbracket_{2,\Omega}} \sim \frac{\llbracket D^{r+1} u \rrbracket_{2,K} h_K^{r+1}}{\llbracket u \rrbracket_{2,\Omega} (r+1)!} \sim \frac{h_K^{r+1}}{\llbracket u \rrbracket_{2,\Omega} (r+1)!} \max_{i=0,\dots,r+1} \left| \frac{\partial^{r+1} u}{\partial x_1^{r+1-i} \partial x_2^i} \right|_K \sim \frac{1}{(r+1)!} \left(\frac{h_K}{l_K} \right)^{r+1}.$$

We assume that the solution presents oscillations when l_K is small compared with the distance between nodes h_K/r . Hence, we define the threshold length $l_K^* = C_{\text{DC}} h_K/r$ and the corresponding threshold error

$$e^* := \frac{1}{(r+1)!} \left(\frac{r}{C_{\text{DC}}} \right)^{r+1},$$

and set $S_K = 1$ whenever $l_K \leq l_K^*$ (or $e_{u,K} \geq e^*$), i.e.,

$$S_K = \min \left\{ \frac{e_{u,K}}{e^*}, 1 \right\} = \min \left\{ (r+1)! \left(\frac{C_{\text{DC}}}{r} \right)^{r+1} e_{u,K}, 1 \right\}.$$

Eq. (32) is the straightforward generalization of the latter formula to the case of multiple variables.

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